

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 12

Acceptance of papers **December, 2025**

Acceptance of papers

Published monthly

Topics

economics, technology, social sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

Digital Object Identifier

Visit the website t.me/scopus_IST2100

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THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

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The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

Electronic publication, Issue 12. 613 pages.
Approved for publication on December, 2025.

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DATA TRANSMISSION CONFIDENTIALITY CHALLENGES IN THE INTERNET OF THINGS

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Abstract: This article examines data transmission confidentiality challenges in Internet of Things (IoT) technologies within the framework of Industry 4.0. The rapid growth of IoT devices and the increasing volume of exchanged data have significantly intensified data security risks. The study focuses on data breach threats, the role of cryptographic techniques in ensuring confidentiality and integrity, and the importance of prime-number-based keys in asymmetric cryptosystems. In addition, the paper discusses probabilistic and deterministic primality testing algorithms and their implications for cryptographic stability in IoT environments.

Key words: Internet of Things (IoT), Industry 4.0, data confidentiality, cryptography, asymmetric encryption, prime numbers, information security.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada Industry 4.0 doirasida shakllanayotgan Narsalar Interneti (IoT) texnologiyalarida ma'lumotlarni uzatish jarayonida yuzaga keladigan maxfiylik muammolari tahlil qilinadi. IoT qurilmalarining jadal ko'payishi va ular orqali uzatiladigan ma'lumotlar hajmining oshishi axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlashni muhim masalaga aylantirmoqda. Tadqiqotda ma'lumotlar buzilishi xavflari, kriptografik himoya mexanizmlarining o'rni hamda assimetrik kriptotizimlarda tub sonlarga asoslangan kalitlarning ahamiyati yoritiladi. Shuningdek, tub sonlarni aniqlashda qo'llaniladigan ehtimollik va deterministik algoritmlar nuqtayi nazaridan xavfsizlik masalalari baholanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Internet of Things (IoT), Industry 4.0, ma'lumotlar maxfiyligi, kriptografiya, assimetrik shifrlash, tub sonlar, axborot xavfsizligi.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются проблемы конфиденциальности передачи данных в технологиях Интернета вещей (IoT) в контексте Industry 4.0. Стремительный рост числа IoT-устройств и объёмов передаваемых данных усиливает угрозы информационной безопасности. Особое внимание уделяется рискам утечек данных, применению криптографических методов для обеспечения конфиденциальности и целостности информации, а также значению простых чисел при формировании ключей в асимметричных криптосистемах. Дополнительно анализируются вероятностные и детерминированные алгоритмы проверки простоты чисел с точки зрения их влияния на устойчивость криптографических механизмов.

Ключевые слова: Интернет вещей (IoT), Industry 4.0, конфиденциальность данных, криптография, асимметричное шифрование, простые числа, информационная безопасность.

INTRODUCTION

As several emerging technologies converge to offer digital solutions, Industry 4.0 has been referred to as a new industrial stage. They cover four basic technologies: Internet of Things (IoT), cloud services, big data, and analytics. The next phase of communication is the Internet of Things (IoT). IoT allows for the seamless creation, receipt, and exchange of data between physical items. Different IoT applications concentrate on automating various processes in an effort to give inanimate physical things the ability to behave autonomously. As the number of IoT devices increases from year to year, so does the amount of data. Consequently, there is a rise in the frequency of data breaches as a result. Consequently, guaranteeing the security of data, particularly its

confidentiality, becomes crucial. Employing cryptographic techniques stands as the most effective approach to safeguarding information confidentiality and integrity. The stability of cryptographic algorithms depends on the key used. In asymmetric cryptosystems, the key value must be prime. Currently, there are both probabilistic and deterministic algorithms for checking numbers for probability, and in practice, more probabilistic algorithms are used. This article analyzes data privacy issues in IoT technology, which is part of Industry 4.0.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The rapid expansion of the Internet of Things within the Industry 4.0 paradigm has significantly increased concerns related to data transmission confidentiality and cybersecurity. Early comprehensive studies by Ahmad et al. in 2021 emphasize that IoT-based cloud computing environments are inherently vulnerable due to resource-constrained devices, heterogeneous architectures, and large-scale data exchange. Their survey highlights confidentiality, integrity, and authentication as the most critical security dimensions, stressing that traditional security mechanisms are often inadequate for IoT ecosystems.

Privacy preservation has become a central research focus as IoT systems increasingly support smart city infrastructures. Kumar et al. in 2021 propose a blockchain-based machine learning framework aimed at protecting user privacy in IoT-driven urban environments. Their findings demonstrate that decentralized architectures can reduce single points of failure while enhancing data confidentiality and trust. Similar conclusions are drawn by Fernández-Caramés and Fraga-Lamas in 2018, who provide a detailed review of blockchain applications in IoT and underline its potential to secure data exchange through cryptographic primitives and distributed consensus mechanisms. However, Nartey et al. in 2021 caution that scalability, latency, and computational overhead remain major obstacles to large-scale deployment.

Several studies address IoT security from an architectural and communication perspective. Salama et al. in 2023 present an overview of IoT and machine-to-machine communications, identifying insecure data transmission channels and weak encryption practices as persistent challenges. In domain-specific applications, Kantipudi et al. in 2021 examine remote patient monitoring systems and demonstrate that confidentiality breaches in healthcare IoT can have direct safety implications, reinforcing the need for robust cryptographic protection. Likewise, Alaghbari et al. in 2022 analyze complex event processing in data centers and show that cyber-physical security heavily depends on secure data streams and reliable encryption mechanisms.

Cryptographic strength in IoT systems is closely tied to the reliability of key generation and primality testing algorithms. Classical foundations of primality testing are discussed by Bressoud in 1989 and Buchmann and Müller in 1992, who outline deterministic and probabilistic approaches to number theory-based cryptosystems. Rabin's probabilistic algorithms, introduced in 1976, and the Solovay–Strassen test proposed in 1977 remain cornerstones of modern cryptographic practice due to their efficiency. Subsequent studies, including Baillie and Wagstaff in 1980 and Ishmukhametov et al. in 2020, analyze the behavior of pseudoprimes and witnesses, demonstrating that probabilistic methods, while efficient, require careful parameter selection to minimize false positives.

Recent research has focused on improving the reliability of primality testing for cryptographic applications. Pulatovna and Rasulovich in 2023 propose enhancements to the Miller–Rabin algorithm aimed at reducing the number of false witnesses, which is particularly relevant for asymmetric encryption in IoT devices with limited computational capacity. Frameworks for evaluating primality testing algorithms are further discussed by Duta et al. in 2015 and Westerdijk in 2021, offering comparative insights into algorithmic performance and security trade-offs. Foundational number theory works by Nagell in 2021 and Koukoulopoulos in 2020 provide the mathematical basis for understanding prime distribution, which underpins cryptographic key generation.

Overall, the literature demonstrates that ensuring data transmission confidentiality in IoT systems requires an integrated approach combining secure architectures, advanced cryptographic techniques, and reliable primality testing algorithms. While probabilistic methods dominate practical implementations due to their efficiency, ongoing improvements are essential to maintain cryptographic stability as IoT ecosystems continue to scale.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative and analytical research methodology based on a systematic review of peer-reviewed scientific articles, conference proceedings, and authoritative monographs related to IoT security and cryptographic algorithms. Collected data are analyzed using comparative and logical analysis to identify confidentiality risks and evaluate the effectiveness of probabilistic and deterministic primality testing methods in IoT-oriented cryptographic systems.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the key problems in the new industrial stage is the extremely complicated technical architecture of the production systems in the Industry 4.0 concept [1]. Industry 4.0 has been referred to as a new industrial stage. They cover four basic technologies: Internet of Things (IoT), cloud services, big data, and analytics. The rate at which physical objects in our environment are being connected to the Internet is accelerating. In 2020, there will be over 8.4 billion linked items worldwide, according to a recent Gartner estimate. By 2022, this figure is projected to increase to 20.4 billion [2]. There are expected to be 27 billion machine-to-machine (M2M) connections in 2024, up from about 5.6 billion in 2016 [3]. M2M connections are used in a wide range of applications, including smart grids, smart retail, smart agriculture, and smart cities and ecosystems [4]. The IoT's history, present, and future architecture are depicted in Figure 1 (Figure 1) [5].

Figure 1. Past (a), present (b) and future (c) architecture of IoT

IoT devices give enemies easy access to consumer data by serving as a doorway for their entry into residential and commercial networks due to their cheap power and low security. Additionally, the IoT is becoming more than just physical items or things. There have been several instances where attempts have been made to successfully integrate IoT devices into the human body for the purpose of monitoring the health of different organs [6].

There are four key levels in every ecosystem or environment for the Internet of Things. In order to perceive the data or information needed to carry out various activities, numerous sensors and actuators are used in the first layer. Based on that, a communication network is utilized in the second layer to transfer the data acquired. The middleware layer, which is commonly utilized in the development of IoT applications, acts as a bridge connecting the network and application layers. Various IoT-based end-to-end applications, including smart grids, smart manufacturing, and smart transportation, are present on the fourth layer. Varieties of different technologies are used by each of these levels in an IoT application, which poses a number of problems and security risks. At these four strata, diverse technologies, apparatus, and applications are depicted in Figure 2 [7].

Privacy (confidentiality), trust (integrity, authentication), nonrepudiation (signature, access control), and availability are some of the most crucial security services needed in IoT. Protection from node capture, impersonation, data duplication, and forensic assaults is also necessary for specific situations. The majority of the in-demand security services may be achieved using cryptography.

A key is a replaceable component of a cipher that is used to encrypt a specific message, and this is one of the fundamental ideas in cryptography. Modern public-key cryptosystems produce keys using enormous primes, which can be several hundred or even a thousand bits and then distribute them to users. The creation of specialized software is necessary to execute mathematical operations on such numbers on regular computers and to construct quick methods for producing prime numbers. Modern security needs dictate that there be such a wide range of these numbers, therefore a deterministic approach will not be effective enough. Currently, techniques to produce numbers with a probability of at least $1 - 2^{-128}$ are employed for this purpose (Figure 2) [8].

Figure 2. Layers in IoT system

Although prime numbers have long been studied, the greatest development of probabilistic testing has received in the second half of the 20th century due to the need to generate large (a hundred or more decimal places) prime numbers for cryptosystems such as RSA.

In a set of natural numbers, the weight of prime numbers is considered sufficient to find them. For example, prime numbers up to 512 bits have a weight of about 10151. The probability that a randomly chosen number from a number close to n is a prime number is $1/(\ln n)$. Hence, the total number of prime numbers up to n is $n/(\ln n)$. Hence, the probability that two people choose the same large prime number is close to zero [9].

As noted above, the generation of prime numbers is one of the main stages of the design of cryptosystems with a transparent key, since they form the basis of the solver of modular arithmetic - the module. In general, the algorithms used to check numbers for primality are based on number theory concepts.

The classification of primality testing algorithms can be broadly divided into two groups: deterministic and randomized. Nevertheless, further research reveals that these algorithms can be more accurately categorized into four distinct groups [10]:

- Randomized Monte-Carlo primality tests.
- Randomized Las-Vegas primality tests.
- Deterministic primality tests.
- Heuristic primality tests.

Mathematicians have different ways to test if a number is a prime number based on its form. Basically, there are different kinds of tests to determine whether a number possesses special attributes or falls within the category of a regular number. Certain tests are specifically designed to determine the uniqueness or distinctive qualities of numbers, such as Lucas, Lucas-Lehmer, Pepin, and Proth, while others are for regular numbers like Fermat, Miller-Rabin, Solovay-Strassen, Baillie-PSW. Testing if a number is prime is easier if it can be written in a special way, rather than if it is just a regular number.

Indeed in spite of the fact that probabilistic tests are, in common, exceptionally productive, they don't guarantee 100% exactness of what comes about. At the inverse conclusion, are the deterministic tests, but their fundamental drawback is the truth that they can be in numerous circumstances illogical to execute. Their runtime is exponential (depends on the estimate of the number being tried) and the time fundamental to test the primality of a given number is greatly long.

The only deterministic primality test is minor division [11]. In this test, given an input number, N , it confirms in case any numbers m , from 2 to $(N - 1)$ isolates equitably N (there's no leftover portion). On the off

chance that N is separable by any m , the number is composite, else it is prime. The advantage of this test is the reality that it continuously returns a genuine reply. On the other hand, for expansive numbers, the calculation is unsatisfactorily moderate. Trial division takes $O(2^{n/2})$ operations to check on the off chance that an n -bit number is prime, which is exponential within the estimate of the input.

Probabilistic algorithms are more practical due to the sluggishness of deterministic tests, though they can falter in specific contexts. Balancing efficiency and result accuracy is essential. The Miller-Rabin algorithm emerges as the top-performing probabilistic primality test, while the LLR algorithm proves the most efficient among deterministic methods. Future endeavors aim to optimize these efficient tests, deploying them across parallel and distributed systems while identifying practical scenarios where they excel [12].

The AKS algorithm, although theoretically significant, is found to be inefficient in practical applications when compared to the practical superiority of the Miller-Rabin algorithm. The Miller-Rabin algorithm is recognized as one of the most extensively employed and efficient methods for testing primality in real-world scenarios. The probabilistic Solovey-Strassen and Miller-Rabin tests often require only a single test to determine compositeness. Overall, the practical performance of the Miller-Rabin algorithm stands out among the presented algorithms. The importance of large prime numbers in information security and introduces various primality testing algorithms, highlighting the efficiency of probabilistic algorithms over the AKS primality testing algorithm [13].

The smallest algorithm in this class is based on the Fermat theorem. This examination process is predicated on the theorem that prominent French mathematician Pierre Fermat put forward in the 17th century, often known as the "little Fermat theorem" [14].

Fermat's little theorem states that the equation $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ holds if n is a prime number. Here, a is an arbitrary number and n is not divisible by a . To ascertain the primality of a given integer n , it is necessary and sufficient to satisfy the equation $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. That is, for each a , n is a complex number if and only if $a^{n-1} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{n}$; otherwise, it is hard to say for sure, but the likelihood of the number grows. When a complex integer n is found to be a pseudo-prime based on a , the comparison $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ is made.

When a number n is determined to be complex, however, and the comparison $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ is not made, this is referred to as evidence of the number n 's complexity, and the preceding number a , which made the comparison, is referred to as a "false witness" of primality n .

Therefore, the number n is selected when a number is tested for primeness using the Fermat theorem. The greater the number a that fulfills the requirement, the greater the probability that n is prime. $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. However, for any arbitrary number a , which is prime with n , the comparison holds for complex numbers n such that $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. We refer to this as Carmichael numbers. The set of Carmichael numbers is an unbounded collection, with $n = 561 = 3 \cdot 11 \cdot 17$ being the lowest. Despite this, composite numbers can be found using the Fermat test [15]. This test's time complexity is $O(k \log n)^3$.

This class also includes the Solovey-Strassen test algorithm. The test can yield an inaccurate answer with a certain probability for complex numbers, but it always properly detects prime values. The test's primary benefit is that, in contrast to the Fermat test, it determines Carmichael's numbers as composite numbers.

The primary objective of the test is to examine a random subset of random numbers for a specified number of iterations, as opposed to evaluating every single number in the entire sequence.

The Carmichael numbers in this instance are defined by the Jacobi symbol.

$$\left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \equiv a^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \pmod{n} \tag{1}$$

The number of prime numbers is given by $\pi(n)$, where $\left(\frac{a}{n}\right)$ is a Legendre symbol.

We apply the Euler criterion in this test. It is widely recognized that if the Euler criterion's condition $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \pmod{n}$ is satisfied for every witness of a prime number that is coprime to n (meaning they do not share a common divisor), then n is acknowledged as an odd prime number.

That is, in the $(n-1)/2$ row of the table of levels of prime numbers, the items 1 and -1 that are created in the column corresponding to the "prime witnesses" a and that are mutually simple with n are the focus of this algorithm [16].

In the algorithm, the main focus lies on the items 1 and -1 that are generated in the column corresponding to the "prime witnesses" a , which are mutually coprime with n . Specifically, these items are located in the row $(n-1)/2$ of the table that represents the levels of prime numbers.

However, according to primeness, nonprime integers that meet the test's requirements are referred to as pseudoprime Euler numbers. This test has an estimated difficulty of $O(\log^3 p)$.

The Rabin-Miller test is an example of a probabilistic primality test that is constructed based on the reliable concept of pseudoprimality.

A popular test algorithm for public key cryptosystem design is presently Michael Rabin's, which was partially inspired by Jerry Miller's concepts. It is known that this approach is an effective way to test pseudo prime integers. The Miller-Rabin algorithm operates in polynomial time and has a time complexity of $O(k \log n)^3$.

It is predicated on the representation of $p-1$ in $2^s * r$, where r is an odd number and s is the number of times $p-1$ has been divided by 2 . The following definition serves as the foundation for the Rabin-Miller algorithm [17].

Definition. Assume that $p-1 = 2^s * r$, where r is an odd number, and that p is an odd composite integer. For every j , $0 \leq j \leq s-1$, $a^{2^j r} \not\equiv -1 \pmod{p}$, and $a^r \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p}$, a is referred to as a "strong witness" (composite) for p . In the absence of these conditions, p is referred to as the number of the "strong pseudo-prime" if $a^r \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ for all $0 \leq j \leq s-1$, $a^{2^j r} \not\equiv -1 \pmod{p}$. For p , an integer a is referred to as a "strong liarwitness" number.

The Lucas test, developed by Lucas in 1891, is a technique used to ascertain the primality of numbers (not limited to just Mersenne and Fermat numbers). It employs probability-based calculations to determine the primality of these numbers.

The procedure states that an input value n is considered prime if, under certain conditions, there exists a such that, for each prime q , a divisor of $n-1$, $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ and $a^{(n-1)/q} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. It is necessary to know the prime divisors of $n-1$ in order to use this algorithm. To date, no complex number has been found that does not pass a certain number of Rabin-Miller and Lucas tests. [18].

A probabilistic method called the Proth theorem is used to determine if a given sort of primality exists in a given integer. Typically, values in the format $k * 2^n + 1$ —where k is an odd integer such that $k < 2^n$ —are tested in this test. If for any integer a , the condition $a^{(p-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$ holds, then p is a prime number. Prot prime numbers are prime numbers of this kind. Prot's theorem allows one to rapidly ascertain if a given integer is prime or not. It takes a very long time, though, to determine whether a given integer is composite (every number from 2 to n must be checked). For the purpose of locating prime numbers inside a specific range, this algorithm is advised [19]. The Proth test has an $O((k \log k + \log n) \log n)$ temporal complexity.

Pocklington and Lammer created the Pocklington test, which establishes whether or not an incoming prime number may be recognized. An input number N is prime if and only if there exists an integer a such that $\gcd(a^{(N-1)/q} - 1, N) = 1$ and $a^{N-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{N}$ for every prime number q that is a divisor of number $N-1$. The prime divisors of $N-1$ must be known in order to use this technique (Table 1) [20].

Table 1. Here is a examination of probabilistic algorithms utilized for verifying the primality of numbers [21]

Tests	Benefits	Drawbacks	Complications
Fermat	- Highly straightforward to execute. - Base for many tests.	- Failure probability may reach 1. - Pseudoprime can pass the test.	$O(k \log n)^3$
Solovey Strassen	Pseudoprimes are successfully announced as composites.	- Euler pseudoprime can pass the test. - Computation of Jacobi symbol adds more computation overhead.	$O(k \log n)^3$
Miller-Rabin	- Fast & efficient. - Euler Pseudoprimes are successfully announced as composites.	Strong pseudoprimes can pass the test.	$O(k \log n)^3$
Pocklington	Very efficient if there is a factor $q > \sqrt{n-1}$	Prime factors of $n-1$ are required to be already known.	$O(\ln \ln n)$
Lucas	Valid for any generic or special form numbers.	- Prime factors of $n-1$ are required to be already known. - In the event of a worst-case scenario, the execution time can be significantly prolonged.	$O(p^2 \log_p n)$
Proth	Very fast and reliable test to decide about Proth number.	Working well only with Proth numbers.	$O((k \log k + \log n) \log n)$

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The convergence of emerging technologies in Industry 4.0, such as IoT, cloud services, big data, and analytics, has ushered in a new industrial stage. IoT plays a vital role in facilitating seamless data exchange among physical objects, leading to an exponential increase in data volume. Consequently, ensuring data security and confidentiality becomes crucial to mitigate the rising frequency of data breaches. Cryptographic methods emerge as the most effective approach to safeguard information integrity. Within cryptographic algorithms, prime numbers hold significant importance, especially in asymmetric cryptosystems. The analysis of probabilistic methods for testing number primality reveals that the Miller-Rabin algorithm serves as a reliable tool for verifying the primality of integers within IoT technology, a key component of Industry 4.0.

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Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2025. № 12

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